

METHODS OF STRENGTH TRAINING OF ATHLETES WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENTS ENGAGED IN BLIND SPORTS

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Annotation. The article presents a theoretical and methodological justification and experimental verification of methods of speed and strength training of athletes with visual impairment, aimed at improving physical performance using weightlifting exercises.

Keywords: sports training, exercises, speed and strength training

Relevance.

In order to create the necessary conditions in our country for people with disabilities and disabilities to play sports, ensure their worthy participation in the international sports arena and provide state support, as well as in accordance with the decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 24, 2020 No. UP-5924 "On measures to further improve and popularize physical culture and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and dated October 30, 2020 No. UP-6099 "On measures for the widespread introduction of a healthy lifestyle and the further development of mass sports": To determine the main directions of the development of the Paralympic movement: the expansion of conditions for sports for people with disabilities and disabilities, as well as a further increase in sports [1,11,21,31,41,51,61,71,81,]

In recent years, among the world's strongest athletes with visual impairments, the density of results has significantly increased and competition has intensified. In this regard, it becomes necessary to research aimed at finding ways to improve the results of athletes, taking into account the systematization of sports training and the development of such techniques that will be effective for people with visual impairments, taking into account the peculiarities of their psychophysical development [2,12,22,32,42,52,62,72,82,].

In the process of physical development of blind sports, speed and strength training occupies a special place. It is known that muscle strength is the primary basis of human physical development and has an extremely important applied value. [10,20,30,40,50,60,70,80,].

Exercises with weights are a simple and very effective means of strengthening the health and comprehensive physical development of our youth. They develop such vital physical qualities as strength, speed, agility and flexibility.

Meanwhile, it is known that training with such stresses allows you to maximize the ability of the neuromuscular apparatus of the student and his volitional qualities [6,16,26,36,46,56,66,76,86,].

The training of qualified athletes with visual impairments is carried out using the experience of training athletes without deviations in health, which does not always lead to the achievement of the planned results. This is due to the peculiarities of disabled athletes and insufficient educational and methodological support for their competitive and training processes [5,15,25,35,45,55,65,75,85,]

In addition, the not always justified sequence of the use of basic training tools, high volumes and insufficient consideration of the peculiarities of the development of the body of young men in this age period do not allow us to qualitatively form a specialized foundation for further improvement of sports skills of athletes with visual impairment [8,18,28,38,48,58,68,78,88,]. At the same time, coaches often build the training process at the stage of in-depth specialization in a similar way to high-class athletes, without taking into account the individual characteristics of athletes with visual impairment, which also does not ensure progressive growth of sports results in the long-term aspect [4,14,24,34,44,54,64,74,84,].

Thus, the relevance of our research is determined by the contradiction that has arisen between the objective need of practice in improving the process of training the sports reserve of athletes with visual impairment, on the one hand, and the insufficient development of scientific and methodological support for this process, on the other. [7,17,27,37,47,57,67,77,87].

The purpose of the work is the theoretical and methodological substantiation and experimental verification of methods of speed and strength training of athletes with visual impairment, aimed at improving physical performance using weightlifting exercises.

Tasks:

1. To substantiate the effectiveness of a special auxiliary exercise "jumping out with a barbell" and the traditional method of preparing sports for the blind.
2. To determine the methodology of speed-strength training of athletes with visual impairment using special speed-strength exercises.
3. To identify the impact of the development of speed-strength training in athletes with visual impairment on achieving the best result in strength and speed-strength indicators.

Research methods. To solve the tasks, the following methods were used:

1. Analysis and generalization of literature data.
2. Pedagogical observations.
3. Testing.
4. Instrumental method.
5. Pedagogical experiment.
6. Methods of mathematical statistics.

Organization of research.

The study was conducted in several stages.

At the first stage – from October 4, 2021 to December 18, 2021, the analysis of literary sources on the research problem was carried out, a scientific and methodological apparatus was formed, an experimental methodology was developed. At the second stage, the selection of special exercises was carried out, the development of a training program for the first stage of preparation was carried out, preliminary testing was carried out, forming an experiment that lasted from January 17 to March 28, 2022. The third stage - the final one (April-June 2022) - included analysis and statistical processing of the results obtained.

The results of the survey and their discussion.

For athletes specializing in any kind of sport, a high basic strength potential is a prerequisite, but in no case a guarantee of achieving high athletic results. Even capacious and intensive strength training will not have a positive impact on the development of special qualities if it does not reflect the specific features of the corresponding sports discipline [1].

In the theory and practice of sports, the main means for developing strength and changing the quality of muscles in the desired direction is considered to be training with weights. In modern terms, this is a systematic, well-planned exercise program, in which an athlete uses a barbell, dumbbells and other projectiles and weights, as well as his own weight. As already mentioned, strength training in any sport should correspond to the specifics of specialization [1].

It should be borne in mind that any method of developing strength, if it is repeated for a long time, will not give the desired result. Methods should be changed or supplemented with one another [1].

Special exercises for developing strength should be done in the preparatory period (in the first half of it), so that there is enough time for special technical and tactical training before the competition. This does not mean that strength exercises should not be used in other stages, strength stages should develop in parallel with the improvement of techniques and tactics of fighting and always be an integral part of them, but in different dosages [1].

When selecting the means of special strength training, the following requirements should be followed:

- first of all, it is necessary to load and develop muscle groups and their antagonists directly involved in sports work;
- it is necessary to take into account the competitive movement in space (to choose such special exercises that completely or partially coincide with the movements typical of this sports discipline in structure;
- it is necessary to take into account the efforts spent on overcoming resistance;
- the speed and strength characteristics of the training exercise should coincide with the characteristics of the competitive movement;
- the mode of operation of the neuromuscular system, characteristic of competitive movement, should also be maintained when performing special exercises;
- the duration of the stimuli, i.e. the endurance component must meet the competitive conditions;
- it is necessary to take into account the state of the body, in which special movements are performed in competition conditions;
- it is also necessary to take into account the psychological state of the athlete, which is closely related to the loads carried.

Methodological characteristics should be based on the choice of strictly directed means in the execution mode of 96-100% of the maximum, the magnitude of the load, the use of a sensitive period of development of high-speed qualities [1].

Two methods are used to develop speed qualities: direct and indirect.

Direct methods: repeated, dismembered and sensory.

The indirect method is based on the obligatory preliminary study of the technique of high-speed exercise: the development to optimal mobility of the joints that participate in the high-speed exercise, the development of the strength of the muscle groups involved in the high-speed exercise [1].

In sports practice, they measure: the pace of movements per unit of time, the acceleration time to the maximum, the braking time, the time of a holistic exercise [1].

The physiological basis for the development of strength are the following processes: reduction of as many muscle units as possible, relaxation of antagonist muscles and preliminary stretching of synergist muscles.

FUNCTIONAL GROUPS OF PERSONS UNDERGOING SPORTS TRAINING IN THE FORM OF BLIND SPORTS

Functional groups	Degree of functional limitations	Degree of visual impairment
Group I	Functional capabilities are significantly limited, the athlete needs outside help during training sessions or participation in sports competitions	Complete loss of vision
Group II	Functional capabilities are limited by sufficiently pronounced impairments	Pronounced visual impairments
Group III	Functionality is limited slightly	Mild visual impairment

Exercises for the development and improvement of strength:

1. Static exercises with your own weight. 2. Exercises with stuffed balls. 3. Jumping exercises. 4. Exercises with a partner: squats with a partner on the shoulders, exercises with overcoming the resistance of a partner, etc. 5. Exercises with shock absorbers. 6. Exercises with weights. 7. Exercises on athletic simulators. To a greater extent, exercises for the development of strength should be used in the preparatory period of training and to a lesser extent in the competitive period.

The manifestation of force with maximum acceleration (for example, the force developed when the jumper is repelled). Exercises for the development of special strength: 1. Running for short distances – from 15 to 30 meters. 2. Jumping by pushing one or two legs in different directions. 3. Jumping in a squat forward-backward, left – right. 4. Jumping up with a pop over your head. 5. Cross-step running in different directions. 6. Chest press by beating [1].

conclusions.

1. The wide range of means and weights used, which are most appropriate for the development of strength, reflects the need for such training, in which the strength of the stimulus should increase.

2. Power work requires a lot of energy. Therefore, it is best done in the form of a separate training session. Such a lesson should be preceded by a rest sufficient to restore the energy resources of the body spent on the previous lesson. In addition, after a power load, rest or specific work of moderate volume and optimal intensity is also necessary, contributing to the activation of protein synthesis and the development of working muscle hypertrophy. Specialized power load, as the main condition causing this process, loses all meaning if it is performed as an addition to other work or in a tired state. [7,17,27,37,47,57,67,77,87].

3. No means of educating strength training can be considered universal or very effective. Each of them can (and should) be of primary importance at a particular stage of training, depending on the level of fitness of the athlete, the nature of the previous training, specific tasks not of the current stage. Therefore, if we talk about the absolute effect of power training education, then it should be associated, first of all, with a systemic principle that provides for an expedient sequence of introducing various means into the training process, as well as an objectively determined continuity and interrelation of their training effects on the body.

4. It is always necessary to take into account (feel) the strength of the training effect of the means set by the trainer. These funds should carry a developing potential in relation to the current state of the athlete's body. If their potential is below this level, they are useless (this is

an inefficient waste of energy), if higher, they are dangerous (they will lead to overstrain of the body and the motor apparatus). The correct determination of the strength of the training effect is objectively necessary for the athlete.

5. The weight of the barbell from 70 to 130% of the maximum allows you to successfully develop strength qualities. If the weight of the barbell is approximately 85-88%, then with three approaches to the barbell, 6 repetitions are optimal.

6. In the training process, the methods of strength development depend primarily on the volume and intensity of the total load and the ability of athletes to carry these loads.

7. The hypothesis about the expediency of using the shock method of developing explosive muscle strength to increase the level of special speed and strength training of weightlifters-dischargers at the stage of pre-competitive training has been fully confirmed;

8. Deep jumps give a significant increase in the absolute and explosive strength of the muscles after the increase in their value slows down and stabilizes as a result of volumetric loads in exercises with a barbell. The optimal dosage of deep jumps in one training session is 4 series of 10 repulsions;

9. The use of deep jumps at the stage of pre-competitive preparation provides a significant increase in results in the jerk and push of the barbell;

10. Deep jumps also provide a higher increase in the level of speed and strength training of athletes:

11. It is advisable to include deep jumps in training four weeks before the competition and perform during the first three weeks 3 times a week. The optimal volume of deep jumps is 300-360 jumps.

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